

Client-Side Heuristic Algorithms for Cross-Timezone Meeting Optimization: A Defensive Publication

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March 2026

Preprint · Defensive Publication · Zenodo

Abstract

We disclose seven components — five scoring algorithms and two supporting subsystems — implemented in When2Overlap AI, a browser-based meeting time optimizer for globally distributed teams. The scoring engine runs entirely client-side with no external AI or machine learning API dependency, evaluating every 30-minute slot across a 24-hour window for an arbitrary number of participants in different time zones. Calendar availability is optionally obtained via the Google Calendar FreeBusy API (read-only; returns only busy time ranges without exposing event titles or attendees). We describe: (1) a dynamic comfort curve that adapts to per-participant custom work hours; (2) a weighted priority scoring model with base/local timezone emphasis; (3) a hard sleep-exclusion mechanism with rankable fallback scores; (4) a real-time calendar conflict penalty using FreeBusy data; (5) a fatigue accumulation model that detects consecutive meeting chains; (6) a country-specific holiday and weekend detection system; and (7) a multi-slot proposal protocol that encodes candidate times into a shareable URL. These components jointly leverage four independent data sources — real-time calendar availability, per-participant custom work-hour ranges, country-specific public holiday/weekend patterns, and timezone-aware sleep/comfort modeling — processed through a rule-based heuristic scoring engine, in a combination not found, to the best of our knowledge, in prior scheduling tools. Additionally, three planned extensions (learning-based personalization, server-side integration, and asynchronous negotiation) are documented at the algorithmic design level. This manuscript is released as a defensive publication (prior-art disclosure).

Keywords: timezone scheduling, meeting optimization, heuristic scoring, calendar integration, fatigue detection, holiday detection, multi-slot proposal, learning personalization, defensive publication

1. Introduction

Scheduling meetings across multiple time zones is a ubiquitous challenge for globally distributed organizations. Existing tools such as Calendly, Doodle, and World Time Buddy address subsets of this problem, but to the best of our knowledge, none combine all four ele-

ments: real-time calendar availability, per-participant custom work hours, country-specific holiday/weekend patterns, and heuristic scoring with organizer priority weighting.

We disclose a client-side heuristic scoring engine that evaluates every candidate time slot against multiple dimensions simultaneously without requiring server-side computation. Calendar availability data, when used, is obtained directly from Google Calendar’s FreeBusy API using the OAuth 2.0 scope <https://www.googleapis.com/auth/calendar.freebusy>, which reveals only busy/free status without exposing event titles, attendees, or descriptions.

This paper documents the five core scoring algorithms, the holiday/weekend detection system, and the multi-slot proposal protocol to establish prior art and enable researchers and practitioners to examine and build upon these techniques. All components are implemented in JavaScript and execute within the browser’s main thread.

2. System Overview

The scoring engine operates on a set of inputs: a list of participant time zones $Z = \{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n\}$, a base timezone z_b (the organizer’s), a local timezone z_l (the browser’s, auto-detected via `Intl.DateTimeFormat`), a meeting duration d in minutes, and an axis start timestamp t_0 computed from the user-selected date in the base timezone. Optional inputs include per-timezone work-hour overrides $W = \{(z_i, [\text{start}, \text{end}])\}$ (default: 09:00–18:00 for all), ICS/GCal busy event arrays E , and a snap interval (default 30 minutes).

If the base timezone is not explicitly present in Z , it is automatically added to the scoring set to ensure the organizer’s perspective is always evaluated. Past time slots (before the current moment) are excluded from scoring. For each remaining candidate slot starting at time t , the engine computes a composite score $S(t)$ by evaluating all participants simultaneously. The top 3 non-overlapping slots (minimum 1-hour gap) are presented with detailed per-city breakdowns.

2.1 Composite Score Formula

The final score for a candidate slot at time t is:

$$S(t) = 0.55 \cdot S_{\text{wavg}} + 0.35 \cdot S_{\text{min}} - 0.10 \cdot S_{\text{spread}} - P_{\text{ics}} - P_{\text{fatigue}}$$

where S_{wavg} is the weighted average of per-participant band scores (base/local receiving $2.0 \times$ weight), S_{min} is the minimum individual score, S_{spread} is the max–min range (equity penalty), P_{ics} is the calendar conflict penalty, and P_{fatigue} is the fatigue accumulation penalty. All per-participant band scores are clamped to $[0, 1]$ after applying weekend/holiday adjustments.

2.1.1 Pseudocode: Slot Scoring

```

function scoreSlot(t, zones, baseTz, localTz, duration, W, E):
  for each tz in zones:
    if tz is on vacation/leave for this day: score[tz] = 0; flag excluded
    h_start = localHour(t, tz); h_mid = localHour(t + duration/2, tz)
    s = 0.70 * bandScore(h_start, W[tz]) + 0.30 * bandScore(h_mid, W[tz])
    if bandScore = 0: flag excluded (sleep)
    if midnight crossing: s -= 0.10
    if weekend(tz): s -= 0.22; if holiday(tz): s -= 0.28
    score[tz] = clamp(s, 0, 1)
  w[i] = 2.0 if tz is base or local, else 1.0
  S_wavg = sum(w[i]*score[i]) / sum(w[i])
  S_min = min(score); S_spread = max(score) - min(score)
  P_ics = sum over overlapping busy events: (overlap/duration) * 0.9
  P_fat = calcFatigue(t, E).penalty
  if excluded:
    return S_wavg*0.55 + S_min*0.35 - S_spread*0.10
      - 0.40 (or 0.60 if vacation) - 0.50 (if base excluded)
      - P_ics - P_fat
  return S_wavg*0.55 + S_min*0.35 - S_spread*0.10 - P_ics - P_fat

```

2.2 Timezone and DST Handling

All time conversions use the browser’s built-in `Intl.DateTimeFormat` API with IANA timezone identifiers (e.g., `America/New_York`, `Asia/Seoul`). This delegates Daylight Saving Time (DST) transitions to the browser’s IANA timezone database (via the ICU library), ensuring correct handling of spring-forward/fall-back transitions, historical rule changes, and country-specific DST schedules without requiring a custom implementation. The system also detects upcoming DST transitions within a 14-day window and displays visual indicators to alert users.

3. Algorithm A1: Dynamic Comfort Curve

Traditional scheduling tools use binary work-hour classification. When2Overlap introduces a 10-band comfort curve modeling realistic human willingness to attend meetings, dynamically adjusted to each participant’s custom work-hour range $[w_s, w_e]$ (default 09:00–18:00, configurable in 30-minute increments).

Table 1: Dynamic comfort curve bands relative to work hours $[w_s, w_e]$

Time Band	Condition	Score	Interpretation
Deep sleep	$h < w_s - 2$ or $h \geq w_e + 4$	0.00	Absolute exclusion
Very early	$w_s - 2 \leq h < w_s - 1$	0.15	Emergency only
Early morning	$w_s - 1 \leq h < w_s$	0.35	Reluctant participation

Just after start	$w_s \leq h < w_s+1$	0.85	Settling in
Morning golden	$w_s+1 \leq h < w_s+3$	1.00	Peak productivity
Lunch zone	$w_s+3 \leq h < w_s+4$	0.75	Break preference
Afternoon golden	$w_s+4 \leq h < w_e-1$	1.00	Peak afternoon
Near end	$w_e-1 \leq h < w_e$	0.85	Winding down
Early evening	$w_e \leq h < w_e+2$	0.45	Personal time
Late evening	$w_e+2 \leq h < w_e+4$	0.25	Strong reluctance

The per-slot score for participant i is: $s_i = 0.70 \cdot \text{band}(t_{\text{start}}) + 0.30 \cdot \text{band}(t_{\text{mid}})$. After applying midnight-crossing (-0.10), weekend (-0.22), and holiday (-0.28) adjustments, the score is clamped to $[0, 1]$.

3.1 Pseudocode: $\text{bandScore}(h, w_s, w_e)$

```
function bandScore(h, ws=9, we=18):
  if h < ws-2 or h ≥ we+4: return 0.00 // sleep
  if h < ws-1: return 0.15 // very early
  if h < ws: return 0.35 // early morning
  if h < ws+1: return 0.85 // just after start
  if h < ws+3: return 1.00 // morning golden
  if h < ws+4: return 0.75 // lunch zone
  if h < we-1: return 1.00 // afternoon golden
  if h < we: return 0.85 // near end
  if h < we+2: return 0.45 // early evening
  if h < we+4: return 0.25 // late evening
```

4. Algorithm A2: Weighted Priority Scoring

The meeting organizer’s timezone receives $2.0 \times$ priority weight; all others $1.0 \times$. $S_{\text{wavg}} = (\sum w_i \cdot s_i) / (\sum w_i)$. The spread penalty ($-0.10 \cdot S_{\text{spread}}$) discourages solutions that heavily favor one participant at another’s expense.

Country-specific weekend patterns are recognized: Friday–Saturday for 12 countries including UAE, Saudi Arabia, Qatar, Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman, Afghanistan, Algeria, Iraq, Libya, Syria, and Israel; Friday-only for Iran; Saturday–Sunday for all others.

5. Algorithm A3: Hard Sleep Exclusion with Ranked Fallback

If any participant’s start-time or mid-point band score equals zero (sleep zone), the slot is flagged as excluded but receives a rankable fallback score:

$$S_{\text{fallback}} = S_{\text{wavg}} \cdot 0.55 + S_{\text{min}} \cdot 0.35 - S_{\text{spread}} \cdot 0.10 - 0.40 - (0.50 \text{ if base sleeping}) - P_{\text{ics}} - P_{\text{fatigue}}$$

The two-pool design ensures that in extreme timezone spreads, the system recommends the least-bad options. Slot selection: top 3 from the clean pool first (minimum 1-hour gap), then fills from the excluded pool, preferring non-base-sleeping slots.

6. Algorithm A4: Real-Time Calendar Conflict Penalty

When FreeBusy or ICS data is available, the engine applies a proportional penalty:

$$P_{\text{ics}} = \Sigma (\text{overlap_duration} / \text{meeting_duration}) \times 0.9$$

where both durations are measured in the same time unit. The 0.9 coefficient prevents calendar conflicts from completely dominating the score. The FreeBusy integration uses the OAuth 2.0 scope <https://www.googleapis.com/auth/calendar.freebusy> — event details are never transmitted. Multiple participants' busy data are merged into a single event array, enabling cross-calendar conflict detection.

7. Algorithm A5: Fatigue Accumulation Model

Meeting fatigue is well-documented in organizational psychology [4][6][7], yet no existing scheduling tool, to the best of our knowledge, incorporates consecutive-meeting detection. When2Overlap examines the 4-hour window preceding each candidate slot.

7.1 Algorithm Steps

(1) Collect all busy events in $[t - 4h, t]$; (2) group by participant email; (3) sort and merge adjacent events with gaps ≤ 15 minutes; (4) walk backward from t to find the longest consecutive chain touching the slot start; (5) select the participant with maximum consecutive duration; (6) apply graduated penalty:

Table 2: Graduated fatigue penalty schedule

Consecutive Minutes	Penalty	Severity
0 – 60	0.00	Normal (single meeting)
61 – 120	-0.05	Mild fatigue
121 – 180	-0.10	Moderate fatigue
181 – 240	-0.18	Significant fatigue
241+	-0.25	Severe fatigue

7.2 Gap Tolerance Rationale

The 15-minute gap tolerance reflects common calendar patterns: back-to-back meetings often have 5–15 minute transition buffers that do not constitute genuine rest [4][7]. By treating these short gaps as continuous meeting time, the model more accurately captures cumulative cognitive load.

7.3 Pseudocode: calcFatigue(slotStart, events)

```
function calcFatigue(slotStart, events):
  window = [slotStart - 4h, slotStart]
  for each participant (grouped by email):
    filter events within window; skip source='leave'
    sort by start time
    merge adjacent events with gap ≤ 15 min
    walk backward from slotStart:
      chain consecutive blocks touching slotStart
      consecMin = total chained duration in minutes
  maxConsecMin = max across all participants
  penalty = 0
  if maxConsecMin > 240: penalty = 0.25
  elif maxConsecMin > 180: penalty = 0.18
  elif maxConsecMin > 120: penalty = 0.10
  elif maxConsecMin > 60: penalty = 0.05
  return { penalty, maxConsecMin, affectedParticipant }
```

8. Holiday and Weekend Detection System

Public holidays and weekends are critical for scheduling but are surprisingly complex: each country has different holidays, some countries observe Friday–Saturday weekends, and mechanisms like South Korea’s substitute holidays (대체공휴일, daechae gonghyuil, where a public holiday falling on a weekend shifts to the next business day) require specialized data sources.

8.1 Timezone-to-Country Mapping

The system maintains a compact JSON mapping of 80+ IANA timezone identifiers to ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 country codes (e.g., America/New_York → US, Asia/Seoul → KR). This mapping is used to determine which country’s holidays and weekend pattern apply to each participant.

8.2 Hybrid Holiday API

Holiday data is fetched from external APIs with a two-source strategy. For South Korea, the primary source is the distbe/holidays open-data project [9], which includes substitute holidays (대체공휴일), temporary holidays (임시공휴일), and election days not covered by general-purpose holiday APIs. The fallback is Nager.Date API [8]. For all other countries, the Nager.Date public holiday API is used directly.

Responses are cached in `localStorage` with configurable freshness windows (7 days for Korea, 45 days for others) and served synchronously from cache during scoring. If a cache miss occurs, an asynchronous fetch is triggered and the display updates on completion. In-flight request deduplication prevents redundant API calls.

8.3 Weekend Pattern Detection

Weekend detection uses the country-specific rules described in Section 4. Both holiday and weekend penalties are applied per-participant in the band score calculation (-0.28 for holidays, -0.22 for weekends), and the combined score is clamped to $[0, 1]$.

9. Multi-Slot Proposal Protocol

When2Overlap implements an asynchronous meeting proposal mechanism that enables an organizer to share multiple candidate time slots with recipients via a single URL, without requiring any server infrastructure or user accounts.

9.1 Proposal Encoding

The organizer selects up to 3 candidate slots (with a ± 5 minute deduplication threshold) and triggers the share function. The system serializes the following state into a Base64-encoded URL query parameter (`?w2o=...`):

Table 3: URL-encoded proposal state fields

Field	Key	Content
Timezone list	z	Array of IANA timezone IDs
Base timezone	b	Organizer timezone ID
Duration	d	Meeting length in minutes
Selected time	s	Primary slot (epoch ms)
Proposer name	t	Organizer display name
City aliases	a	Custom city names (language-aware)
Work hours	wh	Non-default overrides only
Slot options	ss	Array of epoch ms (max 3)
Leave days	lv	Per-timezone leave dates

The state object is serialized as follows: (1) construct a JSON object with the fields above; (2) apply `JSON.stringify`; (3) apply `encodeURIComponent` for Unicode safety; (4) apply Base64 encoding (`btoa`); (5) append as query parameter `?w2o={base64}`. Decoding reverses the process: `atob` \rightarrow `decodeURIComponent` \rightarrow `JSON.parse`. The slot options field (`ss`) stores epoch milliseconds as integers, enabling exact cross-timezone reconstruction without ambiguity. Work-hour overrides (`wh`)

include only non-default entries to minimize URL length. Leave days (lv) are stored as `{timezone: ["YYYY-MM-DD", ...]}` and merged (not overwritten) with the recipient’s local leave data on decode.

9.2 Recipient Experience

When a recipient opens the shared URL, the system decodes the state and renders a proposal banner displaying: (a) the organizer’s name, (b) per-city time breakdowns for each slot option, and (c) accept/dismiss buttons. City names are automatically converted to the recipient’s display language using a paired-alias lookup in the timezone alias database. During the proposal viewing state, the organizer’s city names override the recipient’s local aliases across the entire interface for visual consistency; the recipient’s own aliases are restored upon accepting or dismissing the proposal. The recipient’s `localStorage` is never modified — all overrides exist only in memory.

9.3 Export Integration

Accepted proposals can be exported via four channels: ICS file download (compatible with Outlook, Apple Calendar), Google Calendar direct registration, clipboard copy with per-city time breakdown, and email (Gmail compose or `mailto` fallback). When multiple slots are proposed, copy and email exports include all options with a “please indicate your preference” prompt, while ICS and GCal exports use the primary (first) option.

10. Test Vectors

The following test vectors demonstrate the scoring engine’s outputs for representative scenarios. All times are in 24-hour format. Work hours default to 09:00–18:00 unless otherwise specified. Duration is 60 minutes.

10.1 Two Participants, No Calendar Data

Input: $Z = \{\text{Asia/Seoul (base), America/Los_Angeles}\}$, $d = 60 \text{ min}$, $\text{date} = 2026-03-27$ (Friday). No ICS/GCal data. Default work hours [9, 18] for both.

Table 4: Test vector 1 — Seoul + Los Angeles, default work hours

Rank	Seoul (KST)	Los Angeles (PDT)	Score	Notes
1 (Best)	23:00–00:00	07:00–08:00	~0.38	Seoul evening, LA morning
2 (Alt)	10:00–11:00	18:00–19:00 (prev day)	~0.34	Seoul golden, LA evening (prev day)
3	09:00–10:00	17:00–18:00 (prev day)	~0.31	Seoul start, LA near end (prev day)

10.2 Three Participants, Custom Work Hours

Input: $Z = \{\text{Asia/Seoul (base), America/New_York, Europe/London}\}$, $d = 60$ min, date = 2026-03-27. Work hours: Seoul [9,18], New York [8,17], London [10,19].

Table 5: Test vector 2 — Seoul + New York + London, custom work hours

Rank	Seoul (KST)	New York (EDT)	London (GMT)	Score
1 (Best)	23:00–00:00	10:00–11:00	15:00–16:00	~0.42
2 (Alt)	22:00–23:00	09:00–10:00	14:00–15:00	~0.39
3	00:00–01:00	11:00–12:00	16:00–17:00	~0.35

10.3 Leave/Vacation Scenario

Input: Same as 10.2, but Seoul has leave on 2026-03-27. Expected behavior: Seoul is excluded (hard exclusion with vacation penalty -0.60). AI recommends slots based on remaining participants (New York + London) only. Insight message: “🌴 Seoul is on leave.” Heatmap reflects 2 active participants. Seoul’s timeline row shows diagonal stripe overlay.

10.4 Fatigue Scenario

Input: $Z = \{\text{Asia/Seoul (base), America/Los_Angeles}\}$, $d = 60$ min. Seoul’s GCal shows busy events: 13:00–14:00, 14:00–15:00, 15:15–16:00 (15-min gap merged \rightarrow 180 min consecutive). Candidate slot: 16:00–17:00. Expected: fatigue penalty = -0.10 (moderate, 121–180 min range). If slot is 16:30, the chain still touches (15-min gap tolerance from 16:00 end to 16:30 start ≤ 15 min).

11. Planned Extensions (Not Yet Implemented)

The following extensions are in active design but have not yet been deployed. They are documented here at the algorithmic level to establish prior art. All three extensions require a server-side component (Extension B) as a prerequisite.

11.1 Extension B: Server-Side OAuth and Persistent Storage

The current client-side FreeBusy integration uses OAuth 2.0 implicit flow, which cannot issue refresh tokens. Extension B introduces a server-side proxy that: (a) implements OAuth 2.0 authorization code flow with PKCE for Google Calendar, enabling persistent access via refresh tokens; (b) provides a REST API that proxies FreeBusy requests on behalf of authenticated users; (c) stores user profiles, meeting presets, and scheduling history in a relational database; and (d) issues httpOnly JWT cookies for secure session management. The architecture separates the static frontend from the API server, with the frontend remaining fully functional offline for all features except calendar synchronization.

11.2 Extension A: Learning-Based Personalization

11.2.1 Data Collection

A `meeting_history` table records each scheduling decision: the proposed slot timestamp, which time zone the user was in, the slot’s band score at the time of proposal, and the user’s response (accept, reject, counter-propose, or no-response). Each record also stores the hour-of-day in the user’s local timezone (0–23), creating a per-hour signal.

11.2.2 Preference Vector Construction

For each user, the system maintains a 24-element preference vector $V = [v_0, v_1, \dots, v_{23}]$, where v_h represents the user’s empirical willingness to attend meetings at hour h . The vector is initialized to the default comfort curve values (Algorithm A1). After each scheduling event, the relevant hour’s value is updated using exponential moving average:

$$v_h = (1 - \alpha) \cdot v_h + \alpha \cdot \text{signal}$$

where `signal` = 1.0 for accept, 0.0 for reject, 0.5 for counter-propose, and $\alpha = 0.15$ (empirically chosen to balance responsiveness with stability). The counter-propose signal of 0.5 reflects that the user was willing to meet but preferred a different time.

11.2.3 Comfort Curve Override

When sufficient history exists (minimum 10 decisions), the scoring engine blends the default comfort curve with the learned preference vector:

$$\text{band}_{\text{effective}}(h) = (1 - \beta) \cdot \text{band}_{\text{default}}(h) + \beta \cdot v_h$$

where $\beta = \min(n / 50, 0.6)$, and n is the number of recorded decisions. The divisor of 50 ensures the blend stabilizes after approximately 50 decisions; the 0.6 cap preserves at least 40% of the domain-expert heuristic, which encodes knowledge about sleep patterns and productivity cycles. The default curve always anchors sleep hours at 0.0 regardless of the learned vector, preventing pathological cases where a user who occasionally accepts late-night meetings would have their sleep protection eroded.

11.2.4 Privacy Consideration

The preference vector is stored server-side (Extension B required) and is never shared with other users. It influences only the scoring of slots involving the vector’s owner. Users can view, reset, or export their preference vector at any time.

11.3 Extension D: Asynchronous Negotiation Protocol

11.3.1 Negotiation States

A proposal transitions through states: Proposed \rightarrow Viewed \rightarrow {Accepted | Counter-proposed | Declined}. If counter-proposed, a new cycle begins with the roles reversed. Maximum negotiation depth is configurable (default: 3 rounds) to prevent prolonged negotiation cycles.

11.3.2 Constraint Merging and Re-scoring

When a recipient submits a counter-proposal, they optionally provide their own constraints: preferred time range, blocked hours, and adjusted work-hour overrides. The system merges both parties' constraints and re-runs the scoring engine (Algorithms A1–A5) with the combined constraint set. This produces a new ranked list of slots that respects both the organizer's and recipient's preferences simultaneously.

11.3.3 Scoring Adjustment for Negotiation History

Slots that were previously rejected by either party receive an additional penalty of -0.30 , preventing the system from re-proposing times that have already been declined. Slots near a counter-proposed time (within ± 1 hour) receive a bonus of $+0.10$, reflecting the recipient's implicit preference signal. If Extension A (learning) is available, the preference vectors of both parties are used in the merged scoring.

11.3.4 Resolution and Fallback

If negotiation reaches the maximum depth without agreement, the system presents a consolidated view showing the top-3 slots from each round's scoring, ranked by the combined score across both parties' perspectives, allowing the organizer to make a final decision with full visibility into the tradeoffs.

12. Conclusion

This paper has documented five heuristic scoring algorithms, a hybrid holiday/weekend detection system, a multi-slot proposal protocol, and three planned extensions for cross-timezone meeting optimization as implemented and designed for When2Overlap AI. The combination of dynamic comfort curves, weighted priority scoring, hard sleep exclusion with ranked fallback, real-time calendar conflict penalties, fatigue accumulation modeling, country-specific holiday awareness, and serverless multi-slot proposals represents, to the best of our knowledge, a novel approach not described in existing scheduling systems. The planned extensions — learning-based personalization, server-side integration, and asynchronous negotiation — further advance the design by introducing adaptive comfort curves and structured multi-party negotiation.

Sections 1–9 describe components that are fully implemented and deployed in production. Section 10 provides reproducible test vectors with expected outputs. Section 11 describes

planned extensions at the algorithmic design level; these are not yet implemented but are documented here to establish prior art.

This document is released as a defensive prior art disclosure. The algorithms described herein are implemented in or designed for the When2Overlap AI application, accessible at <https://w2o.datainhands.com> and <https://www.datainhands.com/when2overlap>.

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Defensive Publication Notice: This manuscript is released to establish public prior art for the disclosed meeting-time scoring engine and its supporting subsystems, including (i) per-participant work-hour comfort scoring, (ii) timezone-weighted prioritization, (iii) hard sleep exclusion with ranked fallbacks, (iv) free/busy conflict penalties, (v) consecutive-meeting fatigue accumulation penalties, (vi) country-specific holiday/weekend constraints, and (vii) a multi-candidate proposal encoding protocol. The disclosure is intended to be enabling: for each component we provide precise input/output definitions, pseudocode with default parameters, and test vectors with expected ranked outputs, such that a practitioner of ordinary skill can reproduce the ranking outcomes. The public disclosure date shall be evidenced by the publication timestamp and DOI of the Zenodo repository record (Version DOI, v1).